

Upcycling and -scaling in furniture value chains micro-ecosystems for cascading use of wood

More and more innovative designers establish start-ups that produce unique products from post-consumer materials. According to this circular principle furniture and fittings can be produced from locally recovered wood such as sawmill by-products (shavings, sawdust), logs and recycled wood (leftovers, furniture waste). But for this a collection system for the furniture has to be in place. This is an example of local furniture ecosystem that is made possible through smart collection of old furniture and side streams of production. It starts from the deposit and implies the whole production process a custom-made serial manufacturing of furniture produced. For furniture waste, suppliers are local household waste recycling centres. The value chain is based upon a regional reverse logistics and supply system, tailored to the needs of the specific innovative start-ups and architect's!

Regional coverage and transferability

While a good practice of collecting old furniture is found from Central Europe (North of France) it is assumed that more and more of such start-ups will enter the market as the availability of used furniture and furniture parts and acceptance for post-consumer wood products increases. Designers take into consideration on how used wood can be applied and valorised after a variety of further treatments and modifications. From this point of view, the technology of collection and producing furniture is transferable. A regional limitation might rather be related to the level of recycling options within a region.

Image: nova-Institute

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Local recycling volumes of wood are increased on local level
- ▶ Wood is upcycled into furniture, which enhances the value of the post-consumer wood
- ▶ Furniture applications provide a good lifetime span so that the resource efficiency can be highly improved
- ▶ Increasing the public acceptance of post-consumer fibers within furniture is very important because these products are well-known and identified as high value wood-based consumer goods